

ADVANCED IMAGING OF PARKINSON'S: EVALUATING THE STRIATUM AND SUBSTANTIA NIGRA WITH T₂W MRI AND DATSCAN SPECT

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Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the pars compacta of the substantia nigra, whose projections reach the striatum. Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) are widely used for the evaluation of PD, providing complementary information on molecular and morphological alterations, respectively.

This study aimed to compare segmentation methods applied to DaTSCAN SPECT and T2-weighted MRI (T2W MRI) images in differentiating healthy controls (HC) from PD patients, and to investigate the relationship between striatal dopaminergic loss and structural alterations in the substantia nigra.

A total of 173 volumetric brain images were analyzed, including 91 DaTSCAN SPECT (49 HC and 42 from PD patients) and 82 T2W MRI (40 HC and 42 PD). Data were obtained from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) database (www.ppmi-info.org/data).

DaTSCAN SPECT images were segmented using four methods: Manual, ThreeBox, Threshold, and Atlas. For T2W MRI images, the intensity and volume of the substantia nigra (SN), as well as the integrity and presence of nigrosome-1, were evaluated. The Binding Potential Index (BPI) was calculated for all segmentation methods applied to SPECT images. The correlation between dopaminergic loss in the striatum and SN was determined using Spearman's correlation coefficient.

The ThreeBox method showed the best performance in distinguishing between HC and PD, while the Threshold method had the lowest discrimination power. BPI analysis revealed a progressive and linear trend of dopaminergic loss in the striatum. For T2W MRI segmentations, the separation between HC and PD based on SN intensity and volume was weak. Correlations between SN intensity and volume with BPI were weak and negative, indicating no significant association between these variables.

1. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the selective loss of dopaminergic neurons, primarily located in the pars compacta of the substantia nigra (SNc). This neuronal loss leads to the degeneration of axons projecting from this region to the basal ganglia, particularly the striatum (1,2). This projection is known as the nigrostriatal dopaminergic pathway, and its impairment results in decreased dopaminergic neurotransmission. This pathophysiological alteration underlies the characteristic neurological symptoms, such as resting tremors, muscular rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability (1–3).

The early detection and diagnosis of PD are among the greatest challenges faced by the medical and scientific communities. The variability in clinical presentation, the absence of symptoms in preclinical stages, and the rate of disease progression make early diagnosis of PD challenging (4). These challenges are highlighted by the high percentages of dopamine activity reduction or neurodegeneration observed in certain structures when the first diagnostic tests are performed. Generally, before the onset of the first symptoms, there is a presynaptic dopaminergic neuronal loss of 60 to 80%, detected in Single-Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) scans (5). Furthermore, as the disease progresses, uptake levels may decrease by up to 90% (6,7).

In the 1990s, with the development of radiopharmaceuticals (such as ¹²³I-FP-CIT, or DaTSCAN, and Technetium-99m TRODAT-1) with affinity for the dopamine transporter (DAT), new molecular imaging methods emerged with relevance for PD (8,9). SPECT studies gained great importance, as they allow for the *in vivo* assessment of DAT concentration and can distinguish PD patients from healthy individuals, with sensitivity and specificity above 90% (10).

The images obtained through SPECT are subject to different quantification methodologies, with no widespread consensus in the scientific community on which should be preferred (11,12). On one hand, some studies present manual segmentation methodologies, but these have limitations in reproducibility, time consumption, and intra- and inter-observer variability (13). On the other hand, semi-automatic and automatic methodologies have been developed, with particular emphasis on the ThreeBox and TwoBox methods (14,15), as well as the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) classifiers (16–18).

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is also typically used in PD to assess brain structures and establish a differential diagnosis with other neurodegenerative diseases. This assessment is possible due to the presence of neuromelanin (NM) in various brain regions, particularly in the substantia nigra (SN). NM has paramagnetic properties and easily binds to metals such as iron, which increases tissue transverse relaxation rates. This phenomenon benefits PD studies using MRI, as it results in a hypersignal in the SN region (19–21). Thus, morphological measurements and signal quantification in the SN region via MRI could serve as essential diagnostic biomarkers for detecting neurodegenerative diseases such as PD.

NM is a dark pigment produced in the cytosol of catecholaminergic neurons through the oxidation of excess dopamine into quinones and is stored in NM autophagic lysosomes, where it binds to metals such as copper, zinc, and iron (22). In healthy individuals and at normal concentrations, NM has neuroprotective functions by removing toxic substances from the cytosol and preventing neurotoxicity. However, beyond certain concentrations and due to neurodegeneration, NM is released, carrying metals and organic chemicals that have accumulated over the years. This release into the intracellular space triggers microglial activation, producing pro-inflammatory and reactive molecules that respond to foreign bodies, leading to further neuronal death and NM release. This creates a vicious cycle that disrupts normal neuronal function and contributes to neurodegenerative diseases such as PD (22,23).

Several studies have explored this topic, involving different brain structures, segmentation techniques, and MRI weightings, leading to discrepancies between manual and automatic segmentations (21, 22–28). However, no single MRI weighting has been identified as the best for studying PD, rather, a combination of different weightings can provide complementary information on the structural, functional, and metabolic changes occurring in the brains of patients with this condition. The choice of the most suitable weighting depends on the study's objective, resource availability, and data quality (21).

Both SPECT and MRI are techniques that can assist in PD diagnosis, and to date, few studies have investigated both techniques together (29,30). The combined study of these two techniques is recent and requires further research (21,29).

1.1. OBJECTIVES

This study aimed to compare segmentation methods applied to DaTSCAN SPECT and T2-weighted MRI images in differentiating healthy controls (HC) from PD patients, and to investigate the relationship between striatal dopaminergic loss and structural alterations in the substantia nigra.

2. METHODOLOGY

The images used in this work were obtained from the PPMI database, an international, multicentre, and longitudinal study that gathers data from various clinical centers around the world, including the United States, Europe, Israel, and Australia (31).

This database represents a milestone in the clinical study of Parkinson's disease progression and aims to enhance the understanding of the disease and drive research toward improving Parkinson's disease treatment and tailoring it to each patient.

2.1. Sample

The selected sample consists of images from two groups: patients with PD and HC. In SPECT, 49 images of HC and 42 images of patients with PD were selected. In MRI, 40 images of HC and 42 images of patients with PD were chosen, with these being the same patients who have SPECT images. The HC in SPECT and MRI are different, meaning that the 49 HC with SPECT images are different from the 40 HC with MRI images, as it was not possible to find the same HC with both techniques in the database. The HC dataset is characterized by subjects aged 30 or over, without first degree family history of PD. The MRI images are T2w weighted. The software used for this study was 3D Slicer (version 5.2.2).

2.2. DaTSCAN SPECT Segmentation

The DaTSCAN SPECT segmentation was studied by four different segmentation methodologies: Manual Segmentation, ThreeBox, Threshold and Anatomic Atlas.

2.2.1. Manual Segmentation

The manual segmentation aims to replicate the practices performed in a clinical environment. Thus, a fully manual segmentation was carried out, targeting the high-intensity regions in the striatum. A reference region was evaluated by segmenting a ROI in the parieto-occipital parenchyma. In this methodology, only the most intense regions in the striatum were segmented to attempt to exclude Partial Volume Effects (PVEs). The parieto-occipital region naturally presents some variability between segmentations due to being a manual methodology, however, its segmentation was limited to the same brain region and only the two axial slices showing the highest DaTSCAN uptake were segmented (32).

Figure 1 -Manual segmentation on axial slices of a DaTSCAN SPECT image of a HC (a) and a DP patient (b). Left side of striatum (green ROI), right side (red ROI) and reference region (blue ROI).

2.2.2. ThreeBox

Three fixed ROIs were defined to identify the left and right striatum, as well as the parieto-occipital parenchyma region. Using an image of a HC, ROIs similar to those described in Oliveira et al. (2014) were applied. The reference ROI was modified, extending a few millimeters to extract more background noise information. The striatal ROIs were also slightly adjusted. Their dimensions are $40 \times 60 \text{ mm}^2$, while the reference ROI measures $82 \times 36 \text{ mm}^2$. To enable a more precise comparison with the manual methodology, the ThreeBox method segmented only the two slices with the highest DaTSCAN uptake (14).

Figure 2 - ThreeBox segmentation on axial slices of a DaTSCAN SPECT image of a HC (a) and a DP patient (b). Left side of striatum (green ROI), right side (blue ROI) and reference region

2.2.3. Threshold

The thresholding methodology defines a value above which pixels with equal or higher intensity are segmented. Since the images are normalized, the threshold value was fixed at 50% of the maximum intensity. A visual analysis confirmed that the 50% threshold correctly segments the striatal regions. The reference region was also segmented using a thresholding approach, but with two values: 10% and 30%, where all pixels within this range were included in the segmentation (14, 15).

Figure 3 - Threshold segmentation on axial slices of a DaTSCAN SPECT image of a HC (a) and a DP patient (b). Left side of striatum (green ROI), right side (blue ROI) and reference region (blue ROI).

2.2.4. Anatomic Atlas

The final segmentation methodology for SPECT images utilizes an anatomical atlas of the putamen, globus pallidus, and caudate nucleus, based on a template provided by the Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) ICBM 2009a Nonlinear Symmetric. This atlas offers excellent resolution and detail for T1, T2, proton density, and T2* images (33).

Figure 4 - Anatomic Atlas in a SPECT DaTSCAN image. (a) MNI template and (b) adjustment and extrapolation of MNI template.

In this approach, the T1 atlas was used for ROI placement due to its superior structural definition. However, the ROIs were mapped onto different atlas versions, ensuring precise anatomical correspondence across all imaging weightings. The obtained ROIs were applied to a healthy volunteer, revealing that part of the radiopharmaceutical uptake was excluded in the region between the caudate nucleus, putamen, and globus pallidus, as shown in Figure 4 (a). To address this issue, the originally defined ROIs were extrapolated to fully incorporate the radiopharmaceutical uptake (Figure 4 (b)). The reference region was defined similarly to the ThreeBox methodology. As with that approach, only the two axial slices with the highest radiopharmaceutical uptake were considered.

2.3. MRI T2 Segmentation

The segmentation methodology applied to MRI images was performed through manual segmentation, assessing the SN, nigrosome-1, and the presence of the swallow-tail sign. The SN is a structure that cannot be precisely identified in T2-weighted MRI (T2W MRI) images. Its subregions, the SNr (substantia nigra pars reticulata) and SNc, lack sufficient contrast and intensity for confident segmentation. The SNr can be difficult to distinguish from the cerebral peduncle. The SNc appears as a hyperintense region in T2W MRI but, like the SNr, its boundaries are complex to delineate. In this study, the SN region was segmented based on its anatomical location, encompassing both the SNr and SNc. Nigrosome-1 is characterized as a hyperintense region, though its anatomical position may vary. It is typically found in the dorsolateral and caudal region of the SN, which was the targeted area in this study. The swallow-tail sign is intrinsically linked to nigrosome-1. If nigrosome-1 is not visible, the swallow-tail sign cannot be identified.

Figure 6 - HC subject where nigrosomes-1 are visible (a) and the segmentation of the SN and nigrosomes-1 (b) on the axial plane of a MRI T2w image.

Figure 5 - PD patient without visible nigrosomes-1 (a) and the segmentation of SN (b) on the axial plane of a MRI T2w image.

The segmentation of MRI images involved importing the original images into the 3D Slicer software, normalizing pixel intensity, identifying the axial section of the midbrain with the best structural definition, and finally performing the segmentation. Pixel intensity normalization is a crucial step in medical image processing, as these images are compared with each other, and intensity is a significant variable. To achieve this, the images were normalized between values of 0 and 255, where 0 is the lower limit and 255 is the upper limit, using a 98th percentile upper threshold. This approach provided better contrast between midbrain structures.

In this study, only one axial section of the midbrain was segmented. Precisely identifying the SN is complex, and segmenting a single section helps reduce variability between segmentations. Nigrosome-1 has low contrast, making its volumetric segmentation challenging. The selection of the best axial section for segmentation was based on the following criteria: presence of nigrosome-1 and identification of the section with its largest area. If nigrosome-1 was not visible, the selection focused on identifying the section where the hypointense region characteristic of the SNr and cerebral peduncle was most evident. Identifying the intermediate section of the red nuclei also assisted in segmentation, as its axial plane aligns with the SN.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2016. The characterization of the results involved calculating the following variables:

- The contralateral mean of the Binding Potential Index (BPI) from SPECT images, signal intensity, and SN volume from MRI images for the HC group and patients with PD (including the standard deviation);
- Also, in SPECT, the percentage variation of the variables from the previous point between the HC group and patients with PD, using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ BPI Variation} = \frac{\overline{BPI}_{HC} - \overline{BPI}_{PD}}{\overline{BPI}_{HC}} * 100$$

- Calculation of the mean intensity and volume of the striatum and nigrossomes-1, and the presence, unilateral or bilateral, of the swallow-tail.
- Calculation of the Spearman correlation coefficient and the corresponding p-value for the relationship between SN volume and BPI, as well as for the relationship between SN intensity and BPI.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The studied sample comprised HC and PD patients, evaluated through DaTSCAN SPECT and T2W MRI. For the DaTSCAN SPECT analysis, the HC group included 49 subjects with a mean age of 66.9 ± 8.3 years, consisting of 25 males and 24 females. The PD group for DaTSCAN SPECT consisted of 42 subjects, with a mean age of 60.2 ± 8.7 years, comprising 26 males and 16 females. Regarding the T2W MRI analysis, the HC group included 40 subjects with a mean age of 61.7 ± 9.5 years, of which 23 were males and 17 were females. The PD group included 42 subjects, with a mean age of 61.4 ± 8.7 years, comprising 26 males and 16 females.

Table 1 - Characterization of the studied sample.

Group	Exam	Subjects	Mean Age ($\pm\sigma$)	Genre (M/F)
HC	DaTSCAN SPECT	49	66.9 ± 8.3	25/24
	MRI	40	61.7 ± 9.5	23/17
PD	DaTSCAN SPECT	42	60.2 ± 8.7	26/16
	MRI	42	61.4 ± 8.7	26/16

HC-Health Controls; PD- Parkinson's Disease

3.1. DaTSCAN SPECT

Manual Segmentation

The BPI mean achieved using the manual segmentation was 2.768 (\pm 0.480) for the HC group and 1.727 (\pm 0.409) for PD patients. The % BPI variation is, there for 37.608%. This shows that this methodology is promising, however, the standard deviation is expressive and could lead to false positives. In other studies (9), it was achieved 2.24 and 0.90 for BPI measures on HC and DP patients, respectively. Nevertheless, this methodology is intrinsically vulnerable to the observer on the positioning of ROIs and implies variations on BPI measurements.

ThreeBox Segmentation

The BPI mean achieved using the ThreeBox segmentation was 1.028 (\pm 0.222) for the HC group and 0.509 (\pm 0.133) for PD patients. Accordingly, the percentage variation in BPI between the groups was 50.49%. These results are consistent with findings from previous studies (14). Moreover, this methodology demonstrated superior performance in distinguishing between HC and PD patients.

Threshold Segmentation

The BPI mean achieved using the Threshold segmentation was 2.561 (\pm 0.256) for the HC group and 2.129 (\pm 0.269) for PD patients. The % BPI variation is, there for, 16.868%. This result shows a very close BPI measure. One explanation is due to the fact that threshold values are fixed and pre-defined for every normalized image.

Anatomic Atlas Segmentation

The BPI mean achieved using the Anatomic Atlas segmentation of the putamen was 1.951 (\pm 0.512) for the HC group and 0.774 (\pm 0.270) for PD patients. The % BPI variation is 60.331%. For the globus pallidus, the BPI mean calculate was 1.758 (\pm 0.455) for the HC group and 0.941 (\pm 0.314) for PD patients. The % BPI variation is, for the globus pallidus, 46.490%. For the caudate nucleus, the BPI mean calculate was 1.591 (\pm 0.397) for the HC group and 1.020 (\pm 0.285) for PD patients. The % BPI variation is, for the caudate nucleus, 35.895%. These results shows that the putamen has more evidence of dopaminergic neurodegeneration in the striatum.

Evolution of PD with ThreeBox segmentation

The ThreeBox segmentation achieved the better results in the distinction from HC and DP patients. Therefore, this methodology was used to study the evolution of the disease, being the follow-up visits baseline, 12 months and 24 months.

At the baseline, the BPI mean was 0.509 (\pm 0.133). At the 12 months assessment it was 0.458

(± 0.124) and $0.420 (\pm 0.135)$ at the 24 months mark. The percentage deviation of BPI relative to the baseline is 9.969% for the 12 months mark, and 17.389% for the 24 months mark. These results indicate that PD neurodegeneration is progressive and linear.

3.2. T2W MRI

The T2W MRI segmentations intended to study the intensity and volume of the striatum and nigrosomes-1, and the presence, unilateral or bilateral, of the swallow-tail.

The mean intensity of the striatum was $79.513 (\pm 12.325)$ and $72.047 (\pm 11.891)$, and the mean volume was $43.000 (\pm 6.823)$ and $42.821 (\pm 8.111)$ for HC and PD patients, respectively. These results are poor for the discrimination of HC and PD patients. The means are very similar and have an expressive standard deviation.

The unilateral and bilateral presence of nigrosomes-1 was accounted for. In the HC group, there were 8 images with unilateral presence, 32 images with bilateral presence, and 1 image where nigrosomes-1 could not be identified. In the group of patients with PD, 12 images with unilateral presence, 11 images with bilateral presence, and 19 images where no nigrosome-1 could be visualized.

3.3. DaTSCAN SPECT and T2W MRI

The results obtained with the SPECT and T2W MRI images were correlated using Spearman's correlation. The variables used were the mean intensity of the striatum with BPI, and the volume of the striatum with BPI. The calculated results indicate that there is a weak correlation between volume or intensity and BPI. The p-value is greater than 0.05 for all correlations, indicating a non-significant difference.

Table 1 - Spearman's correlation between the volume of the striatum and BPI, and the intensity of the striatum and BPI.

	Volume - BPI		Intensity - BPI	
	Left	Right	Left	Right
(coefficient)	-0.084	-0.059	-0.018	-0.134
P (p-value)	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05

For this correlation, it was used the BPI calculations for the ThreeBox methodology, given that it presented better discrimination results between HC and PD patients. The segmentation relative to the intensity and volume of SN presented higher oscillation and lower distinction between the two groups, which, in part, explains the weak correlation between T2W MRI and DaTSCAN SPECT.

There weren't found studies in the literature that correlate DaTSCAN SPECT and T2W MRI. However, other more advanced MRI techniques such as NM contrast (30) or T2* (19) are more frequently studied and demonstrate better correlation results between loss of dopaminergic functions in the striatum.

The absence of studies between the two mentioned techniques can be explained by the limitations inherent in evaluating the SN in T2W MRI. The boundaries of the SN in T2W MRI are hardly visible and very complex to identify. As observed through various segmentations, there is no obvious separation between the SN and the cerebral peduncle, and between the SNr and the SNc, which corroborates other articles (34, 35). This limitation is a crucial factor in SN evaluation, as it prevents an accurate segmentation of its region. These limitations result in greater variability of outcomes, which may explain the weak correlation of the indicators, as well as the fluctuation of values in the intensity and volume of the SN, mentioned in the previous subsection.

This study allows to conclude that T2W MRI isn't an ideal tool for evaluating PD. On the other hand, more advanced MRI techniques, including diffusion imaging (36), SWI weighting (37), magnetization transfer contrast (MTC) (35), and MRI with high magnetic fields (38), show potential as quantitative biomarkers for PD.

4. CONCLUSION

The methodologies developed in this study successfully addressed the proposed objectives. The ThreeBox segmentation method proved to be a robust and effective approach for distinguishing between HC and PD patients, demonstrating a high degree of separation in the BPI values. Among the tested methods, it was considered the most appropriate for evaluating DaTSCAN uptake in SPECT images due to its strong discriminative power, reduced intra-variability (owing to the use of fixed ROIs), and its ability to minimize PVEs.

Manual segmentation also produced discriminatory results. However, it's limited by its time-consuming nature. The anatomical atlas-based segmentation confirmed that dopaminergic degeneration in PD is more pronounced in the putamen compared to the caudate nucleus. Despite a higher degree of variability, this method can still contribute to the identification of PD and allows for structure-specific analysis of the basal ganglia.

The threshold-based segmentation, when used in isolation, was not sufficient to differentiate between groups. Nonetheless, it may serve as a preliminary step within more complex segmentation protocols.

The longitudinal analysis using the ThreeBox methodology across baseline, 12-month, and 24-month acquisition periods revealed a progressive and linear decline in striatal dopaminergic activity, reinforcing the potential of this method for monitoring disease progression. Further studies are recommended to explore its application in correlating imaging findings with clinical stages of PD.

The utility of SPECT in assessing dopaminergic function is well established in clinical practice, with a substantial body of literature developed over the past three decades. Although recent advances in MRI have improved its diagnostic potential, in this study, T2W MRI did not prove to be the most suitable technique for evaluating the SN or nigrosome-1 in PD. While minor differences between HC and PD groups were observed, they were minimal.

Finally, the correlation between SN intensity and volume with BPI values was weak, negative, and statistically non-significant, indicating no relevant association. This result may be attributed to the high variability observed in the MRI measurements.

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